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NRCS

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States Department of
Agriculture and other
Federal agencies, State
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Agricultural Experiment
Stations, and local
participants

Custom Soil Resource Report for Chelan County Area, Washington (Parts of Chelan and Kittitas Counties)

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Soil Map

The soil map section includes the soil map for the defined area of interest, a list of soil map units on the map and extent of each map unit, and cartographic symbols displayed on the map. Also presented are various metadata about data used to produce the map, and a description of each soil map unit.

Custom Soil Resource Report Soil Map

Map Scale: 1:956 if printed on A landscape (11" x 8.5") sheet.

Map projection: Web Mercator Corner coordinates: WGS84 Edge tics: UTM Zone 10N WGS84

MAP LEGEND

Area of Interest (AOI)

 Area of Interest (AOI)

Soils

 Soil Map Unit Polygons

 Soil Map Unit Lines

 Soil Map Unit Points

Special Point Features

- Blowout
- Borrow Pit
- Clay Spot
- Closed Depression
- Gravel Pit
- Gravelly Spot
- Landfill
- Lava Flow
- Marsh or swamp
- Mine or Quarry
- Miscellaneous Water
- Perennial Water
- Rock Outcrop
- Saline Spot
- Sandy Spot
- Severely Eroded Spot
- Sinkhole
- Slide or Slip
- Sodic Spot

- Spoil Area
- Stony Spot
- Very Stony Spot
- Wet Spot
- Other
- Special Line Features

Water Features

 Streams and Canals

Transportation

- Rails
- Interstate Highways
- US Routes
- Major Roads
- Local Roads

Background

 Aerial Photography

MAP INFORMATION

The soil surveys that comprise your AOI were mapped at 1:20,000.

Warning: Soil Map may not be valid at this scale.

Enlargement of maps beyond the scale of mapping can cause misunderstanding of the detail of mapping and accuracy of soil line placement. The maps do not show the small areas of contrasting soils that could have been shown at a more detailed scale.

Please rely on the bar scale on each map sheet for map measurements.

Source of Map: Natural Resources Conservation Service
 Web Soil Survey URL:
 Coordinate System: Web Mercator (EPSG:3857)

Maps from the Web Soil Survey are based on the Web Mercator projection, which preserves direction and shape but distorts distance and area. A projection that preserves area, such as the Albers equal-area conic projection, should be used if more accurate calculations of distance or area are required.

This product is generated from the USDA-NRCS certified data as of the version date(s) listed below.

Soil Survey Area: Chelan County Area, Washington (Parts of Chelan and Kittitas Counties)
 Survey Area Data: Version 20, Aug 27, 2024

Soil map units are labeled (as space allows) for map scales 1:50,000 or larger.

Date(s) aerial images were photographed: Aug 3, 2022—Aug 8, 2022

The orthophoto or other base map on which the soil lines were compiled and digitized probably differs from the background

MAP LEGEND

MAP INFORMATION

imagery displayed on these maps. As a result, some minor shifting of map unit boundaries may be evident.

Map Unit Legend

Map Unit Symbol	Map Unit Name	Acres in AOI	Percent of AOI
BuB	Burch fine sandy loam, 3 to 8 percent slopes	2.1	55.0%
BvD	Burch loam, 15 to 25 percent slopes	0.0	0.8%
CaB	Cashmere sandy loam, 3 to 8 percent slopes	1.1	28.5%
CaD	Cashmere sandy loam, 15 to 25 percent slopes	0.6	15.7%
Totals for Area of Interest		3.8	100.0%

Map Unit Descriptions

The map units delineated on the detailed soil maps in a soil survey represent the soils or miscellaneous areas in the survey area. The map unit descriptions, along with the maps, can be used to determine the composition and properties of a unit.

A map unit delineation on a soil map represents an area dominated by one or more major kinds of soil or miscellaneous areas. A map unit is identified and named according to the taxonomic classification of the dominant soils. Within a taxonomic class there are precisely defined limits for the properties of the soils. On the landscape, however, the soils are natural phenomena, and they have the characteristic variability of all natural phenomena. Thus, the range of some observed properties may extend beyond the limits defined for a taxonomic class. Areas of soils of a single taxonomic class rarely, if ever, can be mapped without including areas of other taxonomic classes. Consequently, every map unit is made up of the soils or miscellaneous areas for which it is named and some minor components that belong to taxonomic classes other than those of the major soils.

Most minor soils have properties similar to those of the dominant soil or soils in the map unit, and thus they do not affect use and management. These are called noncontrasting, or similar, components. They may or may not be mentioned in a particular map unit description. Other minor components, however, have properties and behavioral characteristics divergent enough to affect use or to require different management. These are called contrasting, or dissimilar, components. They generally are in small areas and could not be mapped separately because of the scale used. Some small areas of strongly contrasting soils or miscellaneous areas are identified by a special symbol on the maps. If included in the database for a given area, the contrasting minor components are identified in the map unit descriptions along with some characteristics of each. A few areas of minor components may not have been observed, and consequently they are not mentioned in the descriptions, especially where the pattern was so complex that it was impractical to make enough observations to identify all the soils and miscellaneous areas on the landscape.

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The presence of minor components in a map unit in no way diminishes the usefulness or accuracy of the data. The objective of mapping is not to delineate pure taxonomic classes but rather to separate the landscape into landforms or landform segments that have similar use and management requirements. The delineation of such segments on the map provides sufficient information for the development of resource plans. If intensive use of small areas is planned, however, onsite investigation is needed to define and locate the soils and miscellaneous areas.

An identifying symbol precedes the map unit name in the map unit descriptions. Each description includes general facts about the unit and gives important soil properties and qualities.

Soils that have profiles that are almost alike make up a *soil series*. Except for differences in texture of the surface layer, all the soils of a series have major horizons that are similar in composition, thickness, and arrangement.

Soils of one series can differ in texture of the surface layer, slope, stoniness, salinity, degree of erosion, and other characteristics that affect their use. On the basis of such differences, a soil series is divided into *soil phases*. Most of the areas shown on the detailed soil maps are phases of soil series. The name of a soil phase commonly indicates a feature that affects use or management. For example, Alpha silt loam, 0 to 2 percent slopes, is a phase of the Alpha series.

Some map units are made up of two or more major soils or miscellaneous areas. These map units are complexes, associations, or undifferentiated groups.

A *complex* consists of two or more soils or miscellaneous areas in such an intricate pattern or in such small areas that they cannot be shown separately on the maps. The pattern and proportion of the soils or miscellaneous areas are somewhat similar in all areas. Alpha-Beta complex, 0 to 6 percent slopes, is an example.

An *association* is made up of two or more geographically associated soils or miscellaneous areas that are shown as one unit on the maps. Because of present or anticipated uses of the map units in the survey area, it was not considered practical or necessary to map the soils or miscellaneous areas separately. The pattern and relative proportion of the soils or miscellaneous areas are somewhat similar. Alpha-Beta association, 0 to 2 percent slopes, is an example.

An *undifferentiated group* is made up of two or more soils or miscellaneous areas that could be mapped individually but are mapped as one unit because similar interpretations can be made for use and management. The pattern and proportion of the soils or miscellaneous areas in a mapped area are not uniform. An area can be made up of only one of the major soils or miscellaneous areas, or it can be made up of all of them. Alpha and Beta soils, 0 to 2 percent slopes, is an example.

Some surveys include *miscellaneous areas*. Such areas have little or no soil material and support little or no vegetation. Rock outcrop is an example.

Chelan County Area, Washington (Parts of Chelan and Kittitas Counties)

BuB—Burch fine sandy loam, 3 to 8 percent slopes

Map Unit Setting

National map unit symbol: 2g88

Elevation: 700 to 1,200 feet

Mean annual precipitation: 8 to 12 inches

Mean annual air temperature: 48 to 50 degrees F

Frost-free period: 165 to 190 days

Farmland classification: Farmland of statewide importance

Map Unit Composition

Burch and similar soils: 100 percent

Estimates are based on observations, descriptions, and transects of the mapunit.

Description of Burch

Setting

Landform: Terraces

Parent material: Alluvium derived from sandstone

Typical profile

H1 - 0 to 8 inches: fine sandy loam

H2 - 8 to 60 inches: loam

Properties and qualities

Slope: 3 to 8 percent

Depth to restrictive feature: More than 80 inches

Drainage class: Well drained

Capacity of the most limiting layer to transmit water (Ksat): Moderately high to high
(0.57 to 1.98 in/hr)

Depth to water table: More than 80 inches

Frequency of flooding: None

Frequency of ponding: None

Available water supply, 0 to 60 inches: High (about 11.1 inches)

Interpretive groups

Land capability classification (irrigated): 3e

Land capability classification (nonirrigated): 3e

Hydrologic Soil Group: B

Ecological site: R008XY130WA - Loamy sagebrush

Hydric soil rating: No

BvD—Burch loam, 15 to 25 percent slopes

Map Unit Setting

National map unit symbol: 2g8h

Elevation: 700 to 1,200 feet

Mean annual precipitation: 8 to 12 inches

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Mean annual air temperature: 48 to 50 degrees F
Frost-free period: 165 to 190 days
Farmland classification: Farmland of unique importance

Map Unit Composition

Burch and similar soils: 100 percent
Estimates are based on observations, descriptions, and transects of the mapunit.

Description of Burch

Setting

Landform: Terraces
Parent material: Alluvium derived from sandstone

Typical profile

H1 - 0 to 8 inches: loam
H2 - 8 to 60 inches: loam

Properties and qualities

Slope: 15 to 25 percent
Depth to restrictive feature: More than 80 inches
Drainage class: Well drained
Capacity of the most limiting layer to transmit water (Ksat): Moderately high to high
(0.57 to 1.98 in/hr)
Depth to water table: More than 80 inches
Frequency of flooding: None
Frequency of ponding: None
Available water supply, 0 to 60 inches: High (about 11.4 inches)

Interpretive groups

Land capability classification (irrigated): 6e
Land capability classification (nonirrigated): 4e
Hydrologic Soil Group: B
Ecological site: R008XY130WA - Loamy sagebrush
Hydric soil rating: No

CaB—Cashmere sandy loam, 3 to 8 percent slopes

Map Unit Setting

National map unit symbol: 2g8k
Elevation: 700 to 3,000 feet
Mean annual precipitation: 8 to 12 inches
Mean annual air temperature: 46 to 50 degrees F
Frost-free period: 140 to 195 days
Farmland classification: Prime farmland if irrigated

Map Unit Composition

Cashmere and similar soils: 100 percent
Estimates are based on observations, descriptions, and transects of the mapunit.

Description of Cashmere

Setting

Landform: Alluvial fans, terraces
Parent material: Glaciofluvial deposits

Typical profile

H1 - 0 to 9 inches: sandy loam
H2 - 9 to 60 inches: sandy loam

Properties and qualities

Slope: 3 to 8 percent
Depth to restrictive feature: More than 80 inches
Drainage class: Well drained
Capacity of the most limiting layer to transmit water (Ksat): High (1.98 to 5.95 in/hr)
Depth to water table: More than 80 inches
Frequency of flooding: None
Frequency of ponding: None
Available water supply, 0 to 60 inches: Moderate (about 8.0 inches)

Interpretive groups

Land capability classification (irrigated): 3e
Land capability classification (nonirrigated): 3e
Hydrologic Soil Group: A
Ecological site: R008XY130WA - Loamy sagebrush
Hydric soil rating: No

CaD—Cashmere sandy loam, 15 to 25 percent slopes

Map Unit Setting

National map unit symbol: 2g8m
Elevation: 700 to 3,000 feet
Mean annual precipitation: 8 to 12 inches
Mean annual air temperature: 46 to 50 degrees F
Frost-free period: 140 to 195 days
Farmland classification: Farmland of unique importance

Map Unit Composition

Cashmere and similar soils: 100 percent
Estimates are based on observations, descriptions, and transects of the mapunit.

Description of Cashmere

Setting

Landform: Alluvial fans, terraces
Parent material: Glaciofluvial deposits

Typical profile

H1 - 0 to 9 inches: sandy loam
H2 - 9 to 60 inches: sandy loam

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Properties and qualities

Slope: 15 to 25 percent

Depth to restrictive feature: More than 80 inches

Drainage class: Well drained

Capacity of the most limiting layer to transmit water (Ksat): High (1.98 to 5.95 in/hr)

Depth to water table: More than 80 inches

Frequency of flooding: None

Frequency of ponding: None

Available water supply, 0 to 60 inches: Moderate (about 8.0 inches)

Interpretive groups

Land capability classification (irrigated): 6e

Land capability classification (nonirrigated): 4e

Hydrologic Soil Group: A

Ecological site: R008XY130WA - Loamy sagebrush

Hydric soil rating: No